

Investigative Study on Celebrity Worship Motives on Customer-Brand-Relationship (CBR) Towards Tele-Communication Industry in Bangladesh

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Abstract

The method of using celebrity worships motives has a dynamic strategy used in worldwide including developing countries like Bangladesh. Basically, this research papers determines to find out how the Celebrity Worship Motives (CWM) involve to building customer brand relationship among with consumer via a psychological bond. Celebrity Worship Motives (CWM) strengthens the effectiveness of celebrity endorsement to evaluate the brands in Telecommunication sector. Meanwhile, celebrity endorsement is a critical factor and required to evaluate towards the brand endorsement in Tele-communication in Bangladesh. Customer brand relationship (CBR) has been examined within empirically tested with CWM. It has found to be significant research value within celebrity endorsements in Tele-communicant sector. CWM has been tested in this research to evaluate the effectiveness of brand behavior. According to this research paper mostly focus on Bangladeshi context on the perception of customer on celebrity endorsement (CN) with reference to Customer Brand Relationship behavior (CBR) which has significantly remarks on position in Tele-communication. To conduct a research the primary data followed by survey method. Basically questionnaire was the main research instrument and 200 respondents were considered for the final analysis for the survey. Respectively the sample was used in multiple stages to analysis the data along with both descriptive and inferential statistics were also used to analyze the data. On the other hand Hypotheses were tested by using Pearson correlational analysis via 2 tailed tests, correlational analysis, Anova Test, KMO. The relationship between celebrity worship motives (CWM) and Customer Brand Relationship (CBR) towards the endorsed Tele-Communication brand was found to be important in the findings. This research paper concludes a practical implication by explaining the Tele-communication sector how the CWM relates with CBR whilst suggesting propositions for the future studies accordingly.

Keywords: Celebrity Endorsement, Customer Brand Relationship, Celebrity Worship Motives, Service Sector Brands, Tele-Communication, Bangladesh

1.1 Introduction

Bangladesh is one of the developing countries. It is the most populous country and ninety-second largest countries by area, and it is one of the 12th densely populated nations on the earth. Bangladesh economic growth has been unsatisfactory because of global economic declined. Bangladesh is emerging country with market based mixed economic. It's itemized as one the next eleven emerging markets. The per capital income of Bangladesh was US\$ 1190 in 2014. According to the IMF's latest World Economic Outlook, (WEO, October 2014), global growth in the first half of 2014 fell short from what was estimated earlier in April 2014. Due to this slow performance, the IMF reviewed its projection for global economic growth for 2014, from 3.7 percent to 3.3 percent. The growth for 2015 is probable to 3.8 percent. In the superior economies, growth is expected to be 1.8 percent in 2014, and rise to 2.3 percent in 2015. However, in the emerging markets and developing economies, growth is anticipated to be 4.4 percent in 2014 and 5.0 percent in 2015. Bangladesh economic is in the south Asian region, has been revealing to competitive economic undercurrents over the years resulting both local and multi-national brands find head-on brand competitions to determine their respective strategic positions. Accordingly, banking, insurance, telecommunication, retails and hotel sectors are significant segments in the services sector in Bangladesh. As one the key player in the services sector, there are 39 commercial bank has contributed and played significant role in Bangladesh economic. Over the past three decades, Bangladesh has developed from a controlled economy to a market placed economy through a wide range of policy reforms which include reforms in trade policy in every sectors in Bangladesh. Trade liberalization and Tele-communication has been reforms in Bangladesh. During the progress of the overall trade liberalization programmed, the liberalization of service sectors (especially telecom and financial sectors) also received much importance. Service sectors and Tele- communication sectors are rapidly increasingly & becoming the core of Bangladesh economy. In the context of South Asia where growth rates in services sector has been changeable during the last two and a half decades, India and Bangladesh have been the 3 exceptions with consistent growth. The World Bank indicated the value added in the services sector was 49.53 percent from 1980 to 2011. In recently it has increased 55.51 percent in 2011. Accordingly, banking, insurance, telecommunication, retails and hotel sectors are significant segments in the services sector in Bangladesh. There are more than 75 insurances companies helping to Bangladeshi economic. Especially the banking component, insurance companies and telecommunication plays a significant role in Bangladesh economic. In Bangladesh, 6 mobile operators have been providing networks in Bangladesh. According to the Bangladesh telecommunication Regulatory Commission (BTRC) of Bangladesh there are 6 mobile phone services operators and there some fixed telephone operators as the end of 2015. there are some of the multinational operators are providing network namely GRAMEENPHONE, AIRTEL, ROBI, BANGLALINK and TELETALK is local operator in Bangladesh. The number of mobile phone subscribers in Bangladesh as end of August 2021 was 178.61 million, the dramatically user risen from February 2009 to till continue. The mobile telecommunication industry is highly competitive as these operators thoroughly implement a variety of gorgeous packages to cater different market segments. The services sector employment has also contributed to the country's GDP. The employment share of the service sector has been somewhat unstable during the last two decades from 1990s to 2000s, but now it's constantly increasing and helping to Bangladesh economic. In recent year 2014 to 2015 indicated the GDP growth rate is 6.51 percentages and the services sector growth rate was 5.83. There are a lot of national and international company hiring celebrities for promoting their products and the brand. The celebrities are people who enjoy public

recognition by larger shares of certain group of people and it has very competitive in Bangladesh. The term of Celebrity refers to an individual person who is known to the public figure or icon such as actor, actress, athletics, entertainer, etc.) For his or her successes in areas other than the product class endorsed (Friedman and Friedman, 1979). As celebrities has various attributes which has applied in the field area. As reviewing to Bangladesh market, the central bank of Bangladesh (2015) indicates how significantly service sector dominates in Bangladesh economic which has half of the GDP. Garment export and foreign remittance are the backbone of Bangladesh's industrial sector and financial sector economy. In 2015, the total export was 80% of and surpassed \$25 billion. Actually the Bangladesh textile industry is the second largest exporter in the world. On the other hand, the Bangladesh telecoms industry has rapidly growth over the last few years and dominated by foreigner.t further reveals that Banking, Telecommunication, Tourism, Insurance and Transport Services also play a very significant role in the stream of service sector. Branding services has been a very competitive in Bangladesh when it comes to Tele-communication sector. It has been depending on the dynamic forces and serious competition found amongst brands. Bangladesh is sport crazy nation. They like to played cricket, football, hockey, tennis etc. But cricket is much popular compare to other game like India, Sri Lanka, and Pakistan. Bangladeshi nation is much interested to cricket stars compare to cinema stars are found very less attractive.t has found that about 25% of all television and print advertisements in the United States have featured celebrities (Erdogan, Baker, & Tag, 2001). In Bangladesh, celebrities are used in advertising to attract attention of audience and also raise message strength to enhancing advertising effectiveness (Erdogan, 1999). So it seems that Celebrity Endorsement is a widely used to commercialized concept across in Bangladesh. According to the Federal Trade Commission (1980, as cited in Angel, 2009), an endorsement is defined as any advertising message (including verbal statements, demos, or illustrations of the name, signature and other identifying personal characteristics of an individual name of an organization. which consumers are likely to believe reflecting the opinions, beliefs, findings, or expertise of a party in addition to subsidizing advertiser. However, the celebrities are helping to build up the strong economy in Bangladesh. There are some of the multinational company haring celebrities to promote their brand and such as cricketer, TV actors and actresses etc. Basically, when the celebrities endorsed a product and it's very highly effected to companies and makes awareness regarding the companies' product and services.

Source: TheGlobalEconomy.com, World Bank

1.2 The research questions

This paper identifies four research questions addressing to empirical gaps and contextual importance as reviewed.

- A. What is the impact of celebrity worship motives toward in CBR?(Main question)
- B. How does the impact of aspiration motives toward in CBR?
- C. How does impact of playful motives toward in CBR?
- D. What is intense attachment motives toward in CBR?

1.3 Research objectives

- To evaluate the overall impact of celebrity worship motives toward in CBR.
- To examine the impact of playful motives toward in CBR.
- To examine impact of celebrity intense attachment toward in CBR.
- To examines the impact of aspirational motives towards CBR of the endorsed brand.

LITERATURE OF REVIEW

The customer brand relationships are very complex to define as the relationship between the customer and brand, its being connected to personal identification of the customer and brand. (Jokanovic, 2005). Celebrity endorsement is highly applicable strategy to achieve consumer interests or needs and wants regarding their brand loyalty in the marketplace. Pringle (2004) has testified that a high rate of repay (27 times its costs) for this strategy. Brand relation may become an active partner between consumer and psycho- socio- cultural context” (Fournier, 1998). Moreover (MacInnis et al., 2009) argued that psychological and behavioral effects of brand relationships are also numerous and complex. According to Ramesh Kumar (2006) argued that the brand relationship is nothing but to know how people make long-term promises to buy and consume the products and services. How does customer have holding that leads the result to reflect loyalty as certain kind of relationship (Chestnut, 2004). Many authors have assumed that the brand as a partner in a pair relationship with the buyer (Aaker, 1995) (Aaker et al., 2001). Celebrity endorsement in service sector and other business sectors are a highly successful strategy to get the attraction from the consumer significance and brand loyalty in a disordered marketplace. Pringle (2004) has argued a high rate-of-return (27 times its costs) for celebrity endorsement strategy. The Studies on celebrity endorsement indicated a number of methods use in paradigms with source of credibility (Hovland, Janis and Kelley 1953), source of attractiveness and attention of awareness (Kahle and Homer 2009; Ohanian 1990), meaning of transfer (McCracken 1986) and image of congruence (Biswas, Biswas and Das 2006) to realize the effect of the celebrity motives. By evaluating the other communication research, the most endorser research studies follow the postulates of the Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM; Petty and Cacioppo 1980), where a celebrity’s attributes would receive either elaborate or heuristic processing based on the attributes’ perceived relevance to the consumers’ decision-making (Petty and Wegener 2002). Based on the positive opinion of the celebrity, the consumer may associate the endorsed brand but its depending on the product quality and services. McCracken (1989) urged that consumption of endorsed brands further allow consumers to gain the appreciated attributes. Image similarity (e.g., Biswas, Biswas and Das 2006) and relational bonding (e.g., Hung, Chan and Tse 2011) provide extra support for the affect transfer explanation.

It has done by promoting source attractiveness. Brand endorsements by celebrities are a widespread phenomenon in national wide in Bangladesh. For decades, the celebrities present in the Bangladesh

films, TV drama, TV modelers, actors and actresses have provided lifestyle cues to youth. Given the popularity, opportunities, size and scope of the celebrities contemporary in the film industry have the power to influence the brand attitude and behavior of millions of people, particularly the youth in Bangladesh. The several was discussions happened between strategic media work and WHO, after discussing with media experts, sociologists and professionals media people and academies determines that the impact of films and its subsequent impact of celebrities on the youth. The country observed for the first time aggressive competition between new players and big established businesses with the opening of the new Bangladesh economy in 1991. Over a period of time various researchers studied the impact of celebrity endorsements on brands. Their studies revealed that the impact of celebrity endorsements on brands varies with the celebrity and the product category and that most of the endorsements have a favorable impact (Balakrishna, 2011 and Ganesan et al., 2012). Goel, Parul (2013) found in her study related to consumers' opinion about celebrity endorsements in Bangladesh that Majority of the respondents are aware of celebrity endorsements and their buying decisions are influenced by factors like value for money, quality and price of the product and service. Also a major amount of respondents does buy celebrities endorsed brands or products because they think that endorsed products, services or brands carry high image and are of good quality. Majority of the respondents believe that celebrity endorsement helps in brand promotion and help companies to raise their total revenue. At the same time most of respondents narrated that celebrities do not use products endorsed by themselves and it is the sports celebrities who are most influential. Shah, Piyush & Pachariya, N. C., (2009) in their study Celebrity endorsement in Bangladesh – An effective tool of sales promotion found that all the participants were very much aware of the fashion of celebrity endorsing products. Mukherjee, K & Choudhury, A. (2014) found in their study related to Celebrity Endorsement and its Impacts on Buying Behavior towards Personal Care Products found that Celebrity endorsement is a powerful tool that increases the effects of the advertisement campaign. Celebrity endorsement, through mass media has become public sensation in the advertisement world and formed an essential part as marketing communication technique. Consumers are significantly influenced by celebrities and advertisements, specifically the females, are under the three dimensions – Perception towards celebrity, Stimuli on buying decision and celebrity endorsement impact on buying decision. Business houses are capitalizing on the behavioral changes of consumers owing to celebrity endorsement. Celebrity endorsement makes a favorable and positive impact on recall and buying decision. Celebrity along with other mutual factors and elements acts as Stimuli to change the buying behavior of the consumers. The study indicates that both the male and female are highly positive towards celebrity perception as well as sensitive to the celebrity advertisements. Naresh, M. & Latha, K. Lavanya discussed on their study “The CE -Impact of Celebrity Endorsement on buy Decision of Telecom industries user- A Case of marketing Students” received that an impact of celebrities in advertisements on consumers (young) to Identify a Brand in Bangladesh Telecom industry. The celebrity endorsement is effective tools for offline or online marketing communication for any kind of companies. The study found that interestingly young consumers (students) the potential market share holders in high population country like Bangladesh were get impact more by celebrity endorsement strategy on their purchase decision. Age of the certain group of people played a vital role while celebrity endorsing products for promotional purposes. It might always carrying positive or negative attitude for celebrity. It also declared a result that consumer would prefer celebrity based advertisement sources when they really don't know about the brand. Mathur, R. (1998) found that when public personality of the celebrity matches with the products and target

audiences then celebrity endorsers are more effective than non-celebrity endorsers in creating positive attitudes in the direction of promotion and recognized brand and increasing intentions to buying products and services.

Celebrities can influence the attitude and buying decision of the consumers because of the status, credibility, responsibility and fan following enjoyed by them. Celebrity endorsement helps corporations to build up brand awareness and to gain acceptance. According to research done by O'Mahony and Meenaghan, (1998), "The celebrity endorsement can have an impact on the consumer's recall evaluations, consideration and buying intentions. Advertisement is a process that purposes to help the prospective consumers consider the products or services and advertisement with celebrity boost the consumers recall possibilities even further. Dash, Saroj Kumar & Sabat, Deepti (2012) in their study, "The impact of Celebrity endorsed TV commercials on demographic dynamics of attitude: AN INDIAN CONTEXT" found that the use of celebrity endorsers in TV commercials could be effective in inspiring attitudes and purchase intentions. In addition to that the successful celebrity endorsers were used in various platforms for different kinds of products and services. More significantly the success of the use of the celebrity endorsers in the commercials depends on the fact that for which demographic segment the ad was meant—is it meant for males, Female teenagers; white collar workers housewives or targeted students, i.e. for the financially dependents; or it is for the business personnel, for the reason that demography makes a significant difference of the psyche of the consumers. So the marketers should go thoroughly about the psyche of the different demographic segment before finalizing the strategies with a long term perspective. Then only the marketing institution able to satisfy their esteem need, prestige in the consumer's community to gained the desired platform. And this is the only way to reach at the top of Self- Actualization Mountain—the ultimate destination of individual human being as an organization of different activities, the ultimate a group of individuals with a rational outlook.

Sabunwala, Zohra, (2013) in her study related to Impact of celebrity endorsements on brand image and product purchases – A study for pune region of India found that Celebrity Endorsements significantly impacts Brand Differentiation. This finding of the research has also been testified by various researchers and other authors in the past and in few industries like automobiles, FMCG products. They have demonstrated how brand Image has been influenced by celebrity endorsements. Ramaswamy. V.S (2004) investigated the effects of gender matching between consumers and sports celebrity endorsers in an effort to define whether this would upset consumers' perceptions of the attractiveness, reliability, and expertise of the celebrity. They found no significant outcome on attractiveness or expertise, but a significant collaboration on honesty and modesty some of particular subjected area like female endorser indicated more favorable and sometime the male also showing favorable in the output of the endorsement. However, Boyd and Shank (2004) opined that there should be imitation of their study before any kind of generalities can be made, given certain failings of that study.

2.1 Celebrity Endorsement

Celebrity endorser is an individual person who known as a public figure where his or her achievements in areas other than of the product class endorsed (Friedman and Friedman, 1979) Celebrities attachment involved in Multinational organizations to build their brand to recognized in publically for the purpose of purchase motivation. As Indian stars are becoming more famous due to mass media and Bollywood quality films in Bangladesh. As the popularity of Indian celebrity's increases rapidly in worldwide including Bangladesh & it hints a sort of attachment with Indian celebrities like Amir Khan, Saif Ali

Khan, Shahrukh Khan, Salman Khan, Alia bhatt, Deepika Padukone, Katrina Kaif etc. On the source of celebrity cultural similarity and intense attachments with celebrity and number of brand endorsement done by western & Indian celebrities in Bangladesh. Dimensions of Celebrity Endorsement Physical Attractiveness According to Patzer (2014), Celebrity endorser's Physical attractiveness got great social appraisal and acceptability. On the other hand, Bangladeshi celebrities are of their own importance in this regard within social restraints and religious limits. According to the Federal Trade Commission (2007), an endorsement is defined as: Any advertising message (including verbal statements, demonstrations, or depictions of the name, signature and other identifying personal characteristics of an individual or name of an organization). Which celebrities' messages are likely to believe by consumers because of the personality and acceptable trust builder between celebrity and consumers? These opinions, beliefs, findings, or expertise the message appears to reflect will be called the endorser in organization. The endorsements have shown to be most successful in advertisements. A study done by Hastak & Mazis (2003) a product positively and effectively communicates that the product is successful for people who use it (Hastak & Mazis, 2003). Although the celebrity does have some restriction to be found while endorsing products and services for advertisements FTC (1980). "Endorsements disclose the thoughts, experiences and actual taste of products and services with consumers" (Hossain, A, 2023). Additionally, a celebrity can be used for endorsement when the advertiser believes that he or she promise to deliver their opinions relates to products and services. The endorser of brand must be a true user of products and deliver the message via advertisement. The product will be sustained for long time as the same endorser remains a user (FTC, 1980).

Under the celebrity worship motives, there are three crucial components of study. As it has been mentioned above that has categorized Attachment Aspirational Playful Intense Consumers are emotionally connected with celebrity and may take place automatically (Zillmann 1988; 2003). Thus, the emotional investment driven by aspirational motive, the fans are also investment. They may have got result of their playful interaction with the celebrity.

The aspirational motive represents one's need for distinction and is described by celebrities in movies (via action heroes) and games (via sports stars). The playful motive shows one's need for light-hearted distraction to invigorate daily mundane. It can be satisfied by the fun and excitement connected via television and other media to transform one's mood. With these explanations, consumers contrive about and invest their emotions of consumers in celebrities as they engage in media narratives (Green, Brock and Kaufman 2004). By placing themselves imaginatively and emotionally in an alternative world, consumer's better connections with celebrities and meet their entertainment motives' requirement and fulfillment of the business entities. The celebrity and the product are directly associated with the crux of relationship. The celebrity might help to make strength and weakness. But it's depending on the celebrity statues and the quality of the products and services. The celebrity endorsement is widely used for the promotional tools. These strategies have used to associate with a product by using celebrity (McCracken 1989; Seno and Lukas 2007). When any kinds of firms or companies are using a celebrity as an endorser they may see very positive outcomes. The consumer can easily recognize the brand by watching the advertisements. According to Neel wasantha and Hossain Md Amran 2017 & 2023, Advertisement is the key tools to influence the customer between celebrity and consumer. It emphasized to keep connection between celebrity and consumers. It is created worthy ties among each other in the field of product publicity.

2.2 Playful Motive

The second celebrity comment is playful motives that motive to entertainment is characterized by the interest to relax (Zuckerman 2006). Vorderer 2001, 2003 has argued that essentially motivation to the consumer through the celebrity worship motives was purposeless in their selective appearance. The Studies on leisure activities has been confirmed from 27,000 responses that listening to music, watching television and other relaxing activities that required less activation energy as mentioned by Csikszentmihalyi (1997), packaged entertainment with well-versed presentation contents and formats (e.g., Batman, Harry Potter) also requires less activation energy to enjoy (Zillmann 1988). These entertainment products satisfy consumers who seek a sensational experience with minimal investments of ambition, physical and mental exertions (Zuckerman 2006). Extending these entertainment behaviors to the context of celebrity research suggested that consumers who embrace the playful motive would look to their relationship with the celebrity as casual and transitional. Their high-quality of celebrity entertainment trusts profoundly on availability (Example: tuning into OTT platform and Television). Reliable with their fondness for packaged entertainment, these customers attend to the celebrity's proxies (e.g., Oscar Awards, Olympic Championships) that require less activation energy to process. There are three entertainment method contributes to celebrity endorsement in literature. Respectively the aspiration and playful motives holds the celebrity towards the entertainment process of brand endorsement. The element of the trend research studies done by Hossain Md Amran 2017 & 2023, Ohanian 1990 & Kahle and Homer 1985- Celebrity is credible spokesperson and represent the brand value and brand trust with consumers. The entertainment approach also extends studies that examine celebrities as idols (McCutcheon, Lange and Houran 2002; McCracken 1989) that consumers emulate. By expanding the set of motives, the entertainment approach helps broaden our knowledge on how celebrity endorsement works in diverse consumer segments, especially non-fans. Second, the entertainment approach is experiential in nature. It centers between the consumer and the celebrity in several broadcasting contexts such as drama, Television series, movies, shows and games. The experiential emphasis gives this line of research the capacity to integrate the circumstantial productivity of media run into necessary step taken that how consumers attach with celebrities. As studies on celebrity worship reveal, consumers form parasocial bonds with favored celebrities who figure out their way of life, attitudes and behaviors (Doss 1999; Fraser and Brown 2002). To capture these contextually rich and individually specific interactions, the current study proposes that celebrity endorsement effects such as fantasy and emotional speculation are likely inputs in a consumer's entertainment capabilities. As long as an argument, Liu et al. (2007) said that match-up between endorser and product was not as important as attractiveness. The elements of the celebrity impact to build his or her value in publically such as physical appearance, attractiveness and specialized in field namely sports, actor or actress and film stars. Unless the endorser is having high value of demand, despite of unloving to ignore their characteristic towards positive brand attitudes to consumers to increase buying and purchase intentions. On the contrary, Atkin & Block (1983) and Petty, et al. (1983) indicated that celebrity endorsers created more progressive attitudes towards advertising and increase purchase intentions. Further, Kineta (2014), has studied how consumers' emotional investment does relate with brand attitude. Moreover, celebrity creates more positive attitude toward the brand found to be in recent studies (Atkin and Block 1983; Till and Busler 2000; Till, Stanley, and Priluck 2008). Referring to the celebrity source-based characteristics some authors have concluded how those characteristic relate with brand attitude. Amos, Holmes & Strutton (2008), said that credibility plays a very important role in the endorsement's effectiveness

because it is not only assisting in creating more positive attitude toward the advertisement from side to side opinion changes according to product, however, the study refer to an indirect effect on the inclusive attitude headed for the brand and on consumers' purchase goals (Lafferty, Goldsmith & Newell 2002). Nevertheless, most of those studies have been establish in the contexts of unlike physical product categories, and still finds a space to examine the situation and discussing to Tele – communication service brands. The customer brand relationship (CBR) between celebrity endorsement has been further determined in the studies done by Delbaere, McQuarrie, & Phillips (2011), Garretson & Burton (1998, 2005) and Neeley & Schumann (2004). Individuals' studies stated the concept of spokes- character effects on brand attitude towards consumer behavior.

2.3 Aspirational motives

Aspirational motive has driven by the need for achievement, lifetime pursuit, the aspirational motive is characterized by the consumer's aspirations as well as the successful, and glamorous lifestyles portrayed in the media (e.g., watching Dallas, Ang 1996). Consumers who desire to be the likes of the celebrities may gratify their urge through conscious efforts to build and maintain a relationship with the celebrity. The relationship between consumers and celebrity is required to timeframe and alternatively accompanied by energy and financial resources along with mental effort (Holt and Thompson 2004).

Based on postulates transportation theory, as individuals join in celebrity-related activities, they turn into "transported" and engage in the physical, social and emotional attendances of the celebrity. (Green, Brock and Kaufman 2004; Tan 2008). Voderer, Klimmt & Ritterfeld (2004). This study was investigated how entertainment experiences (celebrity fantasy, emotional investment) justify a consumer's playful and aspirational motives. Aspiration may generate an evaluative process involving a comparison of costs and profits (Gilliland and Bello 2002).

2.4 Intense attachment worship

The intense-personal aspect of celebrity worship reflects intensive and mesmerizing feelings about the celebrity, similar to the obsession movements of fans often referred to in the works. Items include as a favorite celebrity is practically perfect in every way' and consider as favorite celebrity to by soul mate'. It is another motivational dimension. People who show this motivation feel that consumers are personally linked with the celebrity. As customers, they think regularly about the celebrity and associate para- socially with the celebrity. In essence, the intense attachment bond "Telecast" what does the celebrity feels emotionally for the fans and how does celebrity share their experiences with fans. This celebrity worship aspect illustrates between the extremes of a rational, distant relationship and a compulsive and obsessive bond that might advance to becoming pathological (McCutcheon et al., 2002). Actually, compulsive and obsessive dimension of celebrity worship motivation is categorized by consumer's willingness and their relationship to extreme and form a pathological tie with the celebrity. This strong attachment frequently affects to the followers to involve in extreme behaviors, frequently going beyond normal judgment and reasoning to be with the celebrity (McCutcheon et al., 2002). This level of celebrity worship will be closely connected to a psychological disorder called as erotomania, characterized in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (American Psychiatric Association, 1994).

In this research study, the authors have examined the two dimensions since they are common among consumers. They propose that entertainment based and intense attachment rational aspects are divided sub constructs of celebrity worship with their own scales of high and low.

By using entertainment based two elements, it is assessed the enjoyment or satisfaction level of a consumers who worship a celebrity and intense attachment dimension assess the strength of the bond between follower and the celebrity person. Through two behavioral dimensions, they are able to attract more

Methodology

The data collection methods include literary sources questionnaire survey, observation & interview. Primary data is original data and collected from respondent to achieve research goal (Hox & Boeiji, 2005). It means data which initially collected by the researcher. This research also adopts Likert- scale technique, in which respondents were questioned about their level of agreement upon certain statements (Colburn, 2003). For this research, application of Likert-Scale in the questionnaire applied to figure out to what extent which respondents think your local authority should deliver the services and your perception and response of current service delivery mechanism delivered in your Local Authority in confine area of Bangladesh. Literary sources are secondary and integral part of the research process (Howitt & Cramer, 2005). In this research, literary sources acquired through computers and computerized databases, books, articles, published journals, reports, seminar and conference papers that related to the research topic. It can also be regarded as a method of data collection for secondary data. Specially highlighting the essentials conceptual framework followed by variable operationalization and hypotheses, sampling method, data collection instrument are more important to data analysis methods to be used. Firstly, it proposes that the intended study will follow a quantitative methodology depending on the nature of the research proposition. This study deals with celebrity endorsement and customer brand relationship (CBR) as main independent and dependent variables respectively playful motives(PM), Aspirational motives(AM), and intense attachment(IA) motives. It could use the validity of following quantitative methodology flowed by literature based evidences given below.

3.1 Conceptual Framework

As per the literature review presented in chapter two, this study has proposed its conceptual framework based on deductive approach to be researched via a quantitative methodology. It has considered celebrity worship motives as the main independent variable (IV) whereas Customer Brand Relationship (CBR) as the main dependent variable (DV). CBR is explained by three variables Aspirational motives, playful motives, Intense attachment motives, the main dependent variable of CBR has been explained by three variables namely Customer-Brand-Relationship (CBR) (Fournier,1998; Veloutsou,2007 & Veloutsou & Tsiotsoy,2010) and Brand Evangelism (Ahuvia 2006; Becerra & Badrinarayanan 2013 & Doss,2014). Celebrity Worship Motives have been explained by three variables namely Intense Attachment, Aspirational motives and playful motives (Hung et al., 2011; Hung,2014; McCutcheon et al., 2002; Ritterfeld ,2004; Yeung & Mcinerney,2005). The proposed conceptual framework further intends to examine the relationship between celebrity worship motives to CBR and Brand evangelism that explain the main dependent variable. Further, it has suggested to examine how consumer personality traits which is explained in the BIG Five Inventory (Costa & McCrae,1992; Goldberg, 1992; John, Naumann, & Soto, 2008; John & Srivastava;1999; McCrae, 2009).

As per the justification hypothesized above, Celebrity worship motives and Customer Brand Relationship (CBR) have been figured out as the main independent and dependent variables respectively. Accordingly, it has developed the conceptual framework as given below

3.2 Hypotheses of the Study

In par with the research questions presented in the first chapter, it has proposed the following hypotheses to be tested in this study.

H1: The positive relationship between Aspirational motives and CBR

H2: The positive relationship between playful motives and CBR

H3: The positive relationship between intense attachment motives and CBR

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

The sample and the responses have been categorized under several classifications. This has been done by using graphical as well as tabular formulations. The data gathered will be used and discussed further deeper in the following result and Discussion of Findings. Total number of subjects in the sample is 200. They were selected by considering different criteria such as their period of study, gender, Faculty, Marital Status, Cultural background. The respondents in this study were made up of both male 60% and 40% female distributed. The ratio male and female respondent respondents are 1.5. This may seem to be gender categories toward effect the outcome of the evaluation on the impact of Celebrity Worship motives on customer brand relationship (CBR) towards service sector at cumilla in Bangladesh. Most 64.5% of students are single in the university in comparing married percentage that also effective change their perception attitudes regarding celebrity worship motives and how does impact to build customer brand relationship

4.1 Test Adequacy of Sample

The KMO is the measure of sampling adequacy in the research, where the variables values closer to 1 are better. The value of 0.6 is the minimum and appropriate for the research.

Test Adequacy of sampling

KMO and Bartlett's Test			
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.			.653
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square		683.307

	Df	120
	Sig.	.000

Based to this table, KMO measure of sampling adequacy was .653 that was more appropriate for the research reliability and validity. This research depends on CBR other independent variables are intense attachment, aspirational variable and playful attachment. There was significant of relationship between each variable that has been shown about mention table.

4.2 Regression analysis: Relationship between Intense attachment, aspiration motives and playful motives towards CBR

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.286 ^a	.082	.077	6.13787	.082	17.632	1	198	.000	1.78

a. Predictors: (Constant), IA

b. Dependent Variable: CBR

It indicates here R value is .286 that was significant (less than 0.05) since positive relationship between intense attachment and customer brand relationship (CBR). The Durbin Watson value is 1.786 that shows there is an auto correlation between IA and CBR. That should be less than 2.

4.3 Excluded Variables and ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	664.246	1	664.246	17.632	.000 ^b
	Residual	7459.349	198	37.673		
	Total	8123.595	199			

a. Dependent Variable: CBR b. Predictors: (Constant), IA

4.4 Excluded Variables

Model	Beta In	T	Sig.	Partial Correlation	Collinearity Statistics			
					Tolerance	VIF	Minimum Tolerance	
1	AM	.085 ^b	1.232	.219	.087	.962	1.039	.962
	PM	.025 ^b	.365	.715	.026	.978	1.023	.978

a. Dependent Variable: CBR b. Predictors in the Model: (Constant), IA

According to this table, this software analysis system already excluded AM and PM value that indicate there are no significant values, if their significant value, but no correlation between each variable. Here, VIF value of aspiration motives (AM) and playful motives (PM) are 1.039 and 1.023 respectively that showed be $1 < VIF < 1.5$

4.5 Pearson correlation

		CBR	IA	AM	PM
Pearson	CBR	1.000	.286	.138	.067
Correlation	IA	.286	1.000	.194	.149
	AM	.138	.194	1.000	.076
	PM	.067	.149	.076	1.000
	Sig. (1-tailed)	CBR	.	.000	.026
	IA	.000	.	.003	.018
	AM	.026	.003	.	.142
	PM	.172	.018	.142	.
N	CBR	200	200	200	200
	IA	200	200	200	200
	AM	200	200	200	200
	PM	200	200	200	200

As per table 11, it indicates the customer brand relationship (CBR) having a positive correlation with intense attachment. The value of intense attachment was .286 that means both are having a positive relationship with each other. The significant value of intense attachment was 0.000(less than 0.05)

The aspiration motives also well connected to the customer brand relationship. The aspiration motives also significantly positive correlation with the customer brand relationship (CBR). The value of the aspiration motives was .138. Here it indicated that, it has positive correlation between the customer brand relation (CBR) and aspiration motives. The significant value is less than 0.05(p=0.026).

The playful motives also significantly positive relationship with the customer brandrelationship(CBR). Where the playful motives value was .067. but it has indicated that there was a positive correlation can be seen on these. Even through The significant value is less than 0.05(p=0.0172) it close to zero and there is no significant value to correlate with CBR.

4.6 Correlation

Correlations		mean	Std. Deviation	gender	Marital	Age	Faculty	Period	Religion	CBR	IA	AM	PM
Gender	Pearson	1.4	0.49113	1									
Marital	pearson	1.355	0.47971	0.013	1								
Age	pearson	1.945	1.0991	.199*	.152*	1							
Faculty	pearson	2.72	0.90315	0.05	-0.106	0.05	1						

Period	pearson	2.25	0.94444	0.119	0.036	0.086	0.094	1					
Religion	pearson	2.175	1.27377	.289*	0.071	0.061	-0.04	.139*	1				
CBR	pearson	22.545	6.38922	.202*	-0.08	0.082	0.046	0.042	-0.015	1			
IA	pearson	14.18	3.12834	0.1	-0.103	-0.016	-0.107	-0.056	0.022	.286*	1		
AM	pearson	11.335	4.54047	0.068	-.147*	-.145*	-0.065	-0.055	-0.024	0.138	.194*	1	
PM	pearson	11.86	5.67994	0.071	0.02	0.041	-0.004	-0.039	0.008	0.067	.149*	0.076	
** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).													
* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).													
c Unless otherwise noted, bootstrap results are based on 1000 bootstrap samples													

According to this table where the age and gender has significant positive correlation that mean age and gender are affected to other CBR. As well as age and marital statuses also significantly positive correlation can be seen that was affected to CBR. That mean age and marital statuses and gender have inter-relationship with each other to below the positive relationship regarding CBR.

Based on the table, the religion and period of study having a positive correlation with each other where the religion and period of study are affected to the customer brand relation (CBR). Even though the religion and period of study are also significantly positive correlation can be seen to the customer brand relation (CBR). Overall religion and period of study have inter-relationship with each other.

CONCLUSION

The current study has confirmed that the celebrity has impact to build customer brand relationship in Bangladesh. It has relevant theoretical groundwork under the celebrity endorser effects. In the recent marketers are intentionally use the celebrity endorser for increasing the sales and build the brand.

These days it is very important for the marketers to understand – stand how their celebrity has motivated customers for buying their products and services. Even through how celebrity has super-facially processed by these consumers. If the celebrity were motivated consumer through the intense attachment, playful motives and aspiration motives that mean, the consumer will influence to buy their products and services as well as the endorsed brand would be evaluated very carefully with conscious detailed. The endorser brands are the “central” route that celebrity having have link with brand.

5.1 Discussion of the Questions and hypothesis

Question 1 to 6 discuss about the customer brand relationship of details. Those are showed in the table. According to the sample selected, all responders are the students of Comilla university. According to their perception in the celebrity has influenced to build customer brand relationship in the service sector in Bangladesh. Overall the celebrity has contributed to build the companies good well in this region. There are number of 120 responders are male and female was 80 who have evaluated to celebrity impact to build customer brand relationship towards service sector in Bangladesh. According to their age, marital status, length of study, faculty and the religion who has been performed to contributed and sort out how celebrities' personality was helped to build the customer brand relationship.

The aspiration motives and playful motives variable were rejected by hypothesis. Which are not supported by given data. The sample area person doesn't have sound awareness regarding celebrity's endorsement. The only one variable has accepted by hypothesis which was intense attachment motives. This variable has performed very well by the Cumilla university students. The intense attachment (IA) and the customer brand relationship (CBR) having positive significant relationship with each other. The most of the people who are emotionally attach to this variable in that area. Overall, despite the limitations, the present research contributes to the match-up hypothesis literature and scope of study by introducing a new match-up feature (Example: value of celebrity)

5.2 Discuss about objective, literature review and variable

The main objective of this study is to present a literature review that examines the effect of celebrity endorsement to build customer brand relationship (CBR) toward service sector brand at Comilla in Bangladesh. In particular, the influence of positive publicity on this assumed relationship is explored. Better insights in the field of positive publicity have been provided and literature has been critically analyzed to identify the main issues and theories with respect to celebrity endorsement. Using this thesis, marketing managers are definitely prompted to pursue a more effective celebrity endorsement policy by which the consumer attitude towards the brand will be positively influenced.

The independent variable is divided into three determinants, which all appears to have a positive effect on the customer brand relationship. According to existing literature celebrity endorsement supports businesses to create a unique embodiment of the brand and bring about a positive effect on the brand attitude towards sales intention (Liu, 2007; Ranjbarian et al, 2010). This ensues from the fact that celebrity endorsers induce higher brand recognition. Furthermore, when a celebrity is positively perceived by the consumer, a feeling of trust will be automatically established towards the celebrity and the approach of consumers will be increased (Friedman et al, 1979).

According to the literature, when consumers find that a celebrity which product and service has endorsed by celebrity has a high degree of attraction, the brand recall and likeability will be higher. Consequently, attractiveness creates an attitude change (Petty & Cacioppo, 2009). The source attractiveness is most beneficial when consumers are low. As they will apply simple decision-making behavior. When the endorser is seen as gorgeous, so the products will be physical attraction of the source will be very significant.

Celebrities are effective because they offer their meaning, power from their public-known character and lifestyle into the endorsement which will increase attitude and increase to company good well. Meaning transmission is especially useful when there is a good match-up between celebrity and brand.

(McCracken, 1989).

Above mentioned theories and determinants have illustrated that celebrity endorsement has a positive effect on the customer brand relationship. However, when positive publicity controls this relationship with the consumer, this relation can help into bring his/her life style, personality etc. (Till & Shrimp, 1998). People may feel sympathy for the celebrity endorser and they have seemed more interested in their own choice celebrity. Therefore, attitude will be positively influenced and consumers buying their accompanying products the celebrity are endorsing (Bergeret al, 2007).

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QUESTIONNAIRE

Confidential

Survey questionnaire

Dear respondent

This questionnaire aims to collect data that will be used in academic research. The survey measures perceptions on the Customer brand relationship service industry. Please indicate the level of importance of each statement has for you. Your comment is highly important for the analysis, and will be treated with anonymity and confidentiality.

Instructions: When you respond for the questions given below, you are supposed to circle the relevant number that explains your perceived response. The values are assigned in the following scale.

1- Strongly disagree, 2-Disagree, 3- Neither disagree nor agree, 4-Agree and 5- Stronglyagree.

4.	I will be willing to be informed about endorsed celebrity brand in the future					
5	I am willing to give feedback to the managers of endorsed celebrity brand					
6.	I care about the developments relevant to endorsed celebrity brand					

No		1	2	3	4	5
	Customer-Brand-Relationship (CBR)					
1.	I want to be informed about my preferred brand					
2	I am more willing to learn news about endorsed celebrity brand					
3.	I listen with interest to information about endorsed celebrity brand					
	Intense Attachment					
8.	Feeling like it happens to me when something bad happens to Celebrity					
9.	Feeling as own failure when celebrity failed					
10.	Difficulty to replace the connectiveness with celebrity					
11.	I prefer to give parity for the advertisement endorsed by favorite celebrity					
	Aspirational Motives					
12.	I need a life goal					
13.	I need a role model					
14.	I need a career model					
	Playful motives					

15.	Learning life story of celebrity is a fun					
16.	Feel celebrity as easy-going					
17.	Find the celebrity as personally attractive					